

Cadmium(II) ion selective electrode based on pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone

Susheel Kumar Sindhu^a, Dharmendra Singh Siddhu^a, Himanshu Agarwal^b and Sulekh Chandra^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, S.S.V. (P.G.) College, Hapur, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Zakir Hussain College (University of Delhi), J. L. Nehru Marg, New Delhi-110 002, India

E-mail : himan_007@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 13 August 2004, revised 1 November 2004, accepted 2 February 2005

A new polyvinyl chloride (PVC) membrane electrode based on pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone was prepared using 2-nitrophenyl-octyl ether as plasticizer for Cd^{II} selective sensor. The sensor exhibits a Nernstian response for Cd^{II} ion over a wide concentration range (5×10^{-2} – 2×10^{-5} M). The electrode assembly works between pH 2.5–7.0, exhibits a response time of <20 s and performed satisfactorily over a period of 3–4 months with good reproducibility. The electrode exhibits excellent selectivity of the order of 10^{-3} over a number of bivalent cations and also demonstrates its utility as an indicator electrode in the potentiometric titration of Cd²⁺ with EDTA.

A number of electrode systems, based on Ag₂S/CdS mixture¹ and other materials² have been reported for the potentiometric determination of Cd^{II} ion. In this paper, a highly selective PVC membrane electrode for Cd^{II} ion based on pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (**1**) as an ionophore has been reported.

Pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone

1

Results and discussion

The potentiometric responses of the plasticized PVC based electrode, incorporating pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone as an ionophore towards a wide variety of metal ions, including alkali, alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions were tested (Fig. 1). The average time required for the electrode to reach a potential within ± 1 mV of the final equilibrium value after successive immersion of a series of Cd^{II} solutions, each having a 10-fold difference in concentrations, was measured. The static response time thus obtained was <20 s for concentrations $\leq 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ M. The membrane sensor prepared could be used for at least 3–4 months without any measurable diver-

Fig. 1. Potential response of various ion-selective electrodes based on pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone.

gence. As seen, among these metals ions the slope of the corresponding potential – pM plots is much lower than the expected Nernstian slope, except for Cd^{II} ion. The results obtained clearly indicated that Cd^{II} ions are more easily attracted to the PVC based electrode, incorporating pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in a wide range.

Table 1. Performance characteristics of PVC based pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone electrode at different temperatures

Temp. (°C)	Slope (mV/decade)	Usable concentration range (<i>M</i>)	E^0 (mV)	Response time (s)
25	30.0	$2.0 \times 10^{-6} - 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$	250	≤ 20
35	30.5	$2.0 \times 10^{-6} - 2.5 \times 10^{-3}$	266	≤ 20
45	31.5	$2.5 \times 10^{-6} - 2.3 \times 10^{-3}$	272	≤ 20
55	32.5	$6.0 \times 10^{-6} - 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$	276	≤ 25
60	33.0	$1.0 \times 10^{-5} - 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$	282	≤ 30
65	44.5	$1.0 \times 10^{-5} - 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$	290	≤ 30

The electrode potentials were reproducible and remained stable for 10 min after which a very slow divergence was observed. The slow divergence in potentiometric response of the sensor may be attributed as it is observed that the pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone coordinated to cadmium(II), which remains stable in DMSO for a few days and then turns dirty yellow, which may be explained on the basis that the complex undergoes desulfurization forming CdS and pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde semicarbazone.

The emf response of the membrane at varying concentrations of cadmium ions (Fig. 1) indicates a rectilinear range from 5×10^{-2} – 2×10^{-5} *M*. The slope of the calibration curves was 29.6 mV/decade change in Cd^{II} concentration. The limit of detection, as evaluated from the intersection of the two extrapolated segments of the calibration graph, was 9×10^{-6} *M*.

The pH dependence of the electrode for cadmium ion at 1.0×10^{-2} *M* concentration shows no significant change in potentiometric response in the pH range of 2.5–7.0.

Effect of temperature of the test solution :

Calibration graphs (cell potential, E_{cell} versus pCd) were constructed at test solution temperatures (25, 35, 45, 50, 60 and 65°C) for PVC based electrode, incorporating pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone. The slope usable concentration range, the standard cell potential (E^0) and response time of the electrode corresponding to each temperature are shown in Table 1. It is clear that the electrode has a Nernstian response in the temperature range 25–65°C. For the determination of isothermal coefficient (dE^0/dt) of the cell, the standard cell potential (E^0) at different temperatures were obtained from the calibration graphs as the intercepts at pCd = 0 and plotted against ($t - 25$) where t is the temperature of the test solution. The resultant plot is a straight line.

The slopes of the straight line obtained represent the

isothermal coefficient of the cell, amounting to 6.2×10^{-4} V/°C, revealing a practically good thermal stability of the cell.

The selectivity of the membrane electrode was tested by its potential response measurements in the presence of a wide variety of cations including alkali, alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions. The selectivity coefficients, $K^{\text{Pot}}_{\text{Cd}}$, were evaluated graphically by the fixed interference method⁴ from potential measurements on solutions containing a fixed concentration of interfering ions (M^{n+}) (1×10^{-4} *M*) and the amount of primary ions (Cd^{II} ion, in this case) be varied, according to the eq. (1) :

$$\log K_{ij} = \log \{ 10^{[E_{i+j} - E_i/m] - 1} \} + \log a_i - z_i/z_j \log a_j \quad (1)$$

where K_{ij} = selectivity coefficients; E_{i+j} = membrane potential in presence of foreign ion j ; E_i = membrane potential when i is alone; m = slope of calibration curve. a_i = activity of primary ion; a_j = activity of foreign ion; z_i = charge of primary ion; z_j = charge of foreign ion. It is seen from the data (Table 2) that in presence of bivalent interfer-

Table 2

Interfering ions	$K^{\text{Pot}}_{\text{Cd}}$
NH ₄ ⁺	23.32
Na ⁺	32.32
K ⁺	25.36
Cu ²⁺	2.3×10^{-3}
Sr ²⁺	2.7×10^{-3}
Ba ²⁺	2.2×10^{-3}
Fe ²⁺	4.3×10^{-3}
Mn ²⁺	3.2×10^{-3}
Co ²⁺	2.8×10^{-3}
Ni ²⁺	3.6×10^{-3}
Cu ²⁺	4.5×10^{-3}
Zn ²⁺	5.0×10^{-3}
Hg ²⁺	5.8×10^{-3}
Pb ²⁺	1.4×10^{-3}

ing ions, the selectivity coefficients are in the order of 10^{-3} , which seems to indicate that these metal ions have insignificant disturbance on the performance of the Cd^{2+} ion-selective electrodes, however, the monovalent ions interfere.

The proposed Cd^{II} membrane sensor was successfully applied to the titration of a EDTA solution with Cd^{II} ion solution.

Experimental

All reagents used were of analytical grade. Doubly distilled water was used throughout. Pyridine-3-carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (**1**) obtained commercially from Fluka, AG and was of highest purity available and used without any purification. The plasticizer, 2-nitrophenyl octyl ether (NPOE) and high molecular weight PVC (both from Aldrich) were used as received.

Electrode preparation :

The membrane electrode was prepared using the method as reported in the literature⁵. The sensor material (5 mg) with NPOE (200 mg) as plasticizer and about 160 mg of PVC were dissolved in 5–6 mL of tetrahydrofuran (THF). The THF solution was evaporated slowly at room temperature until an oily concentrated mixture was obtained. A Pyrex-tube (3–5 mm, i.d.) was dipped into the mixture for about 5–10 min so that a semi-transparent membrane for about 0.4 mm thickness was formed. The tube was then pulled out from the mixture and kept at room temperature for about 1 h. A silver-silver chloride wire was inserted and the electrode was filled with an inner filling solution containing 0.01 Cd^{II} ion solution. The electrode was finally conditioned by keeping for 36 h in a 0.001 M solution of cadmium nitrate and stored in the same solution when not in use.

All the potentiometric measurements were made with a pH Meter (Elico-L1-Model-120). The electrochemical system was as follows :

The performance of the electrodes was investigated by measuring the emfs on cadmium nitrate solutions prepared in the concentration range of 10^{-1} – 10^{-9} M by several dilutions of the standards stock solution by deionized water. As the pH of pure solution lies in the functional range of the sensor, one does not require any pH-adjustment.

References

1. W. Ross, in R. A. Drust (ed.), "Ion-Selective Electrodes", NBS Special Publication No. 314, Government Printing Office, Washington, 1969; H. Hirata, K. Higashiyama and K. Date, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **51**, 209; S. Frant and J. W. Ross, US Patent No. 3591464, 6 July 1971; H. Hirata and K. Date, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1973, **46**, 1468; Yu. G. Valsov, Yu. E. Ermalenko and K. Kolodnikove, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1981, **36**, 889; Yu. G. Valsov, E. A. Bychkov, A. D. Safarov, P. P. Antonov and M. S. Miloshova, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1985, **40**, 1438; R. D. Tsingareli, I. P. Nikolenko, A. F. Radchenko and S. P. Chukov, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1986, **41**, 449.
2. O. P. Ryabushko, A. T. Pilipenko, Yu. S. Savin and L. A. Batkovskaya, *Ukr. Khim. Zh.*, 1990, **56**, 263; S. K. Srivastava, V. K. Tiwari and H. Vardhan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 625; A. P. Gupta, H. Agarwal and S. Ikram, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **6**, 107.
3. L. I. Antropov, "Theoretical Electrochemistry", Mir, Moscow 1972.
4. Y. Umezawa, (ed.), "Handbook of Ion Selective Electrodes : Selectivity Coefficients", CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 1990.
5. M. H. Mashhadizadeh, A. Momeni and R. Razavi, *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 2002, **462**, 425.